

Factors Affecting the Efficiency of the Solar Panel and How to Reduce the Energy Waste

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Abstract:

Renewable energy is now becoming more and more popular due to several reasons. It is an alternative to the traditional energy where in the byproduct of the traditional energy will cause the pollution to the environment. But the renewable energy is not contributing to the pollution. Hence it is called a green energy. The most popular renewable energy is the solar energy. A commercial solar energy as well as domestic decentralised solar energy can be generated. Solar energy is generated using the Photovoltaic cells which are exposed to the sun. The major problem in the solar energy is the efficiency. Today the solar panels are able to generate the energy at around 18% to 20% efficiency. Various methods to improve the efficiency is under research activity. The energy produced from the solar panel when sent to the battery backup for the storage there will be certain loss in the energy through the wires. The loss in the energy will be in the form of heat. This paper gives the various causes for the less efficiency in the solar energy. The paper also explains how to minimize the loss in the solar energy production at the installation site. The paper also suggests the procedure for the installation of the solar energy system.

1. Introduction

India is investing a large amount of money towards the renewable energy like solar energy, wind energy, tidal energy, bio gas energy etc [1]. These energy resources are called renewable energy resources having a lot of advantages to the nature. The most popular renewable energy resource used is solar energy[2]. This energy can be obtained where ever there is a sunlight available throughout the day. The solar energy installation is easy and cost effective. So it is possible to generate the solar plants at either in a commercial production or in a domestic production. More than any other renewable energy system solar energy system has become more and more popular.

The solar energy system has nearly 20% efficiency [3]. Various factors which influence the efficiency of the solar panel. The major factors include the impurities in the silicon photo crystalline[4], deposition of dust particles on the surface of the solar panel, angle of incident of sun light to the panel, the temperature etc. Another major factor effecting the efficiency is the power loss in the conducting medium as it is offering the resistance to the flow of current[5].

The individual silicon cell which converts photon energy into electrons itself has some resistance due to impurities in the PN Junction.[6] This impurities offer resistance to the flow of current through the PN junction. The solution to this is the reduction of impurities from the

silicon cell. This can be achieved by means of the nano technology using nano photo cells for the conversion of light energy into electric energy[7]

Another major reason for the solar panel efficiency is that the angle of incident of sun light which keeps on changing from morning till evening. This results in variation in the solar energy production. The ideal time for the solar energy production is from 10.00 am to 2.00 pm. But the sun light is available from morning 7.00 am to 4.00 pm which can be utilised for electricity production from solar panel[8].

Another factor which effect the performance of the panel is the dust particle deposited on the panel. Day by day this dust layer thicken and due to this the performance of the panel reduces. Around 7% per month degradation is observed in the power efficiency is observed. [9]. This problem can be solved by periodically cleaning the panels[10].

The impact of the dust particle on the solar panel may not be considerable for small plants as they produce electricity at a small range whereas the impact of the dust particle on the surface of the panel is considerably large for the plants which are producing gigawatts of power.

2. Objective

- The main objective is to propose a model which minimises the energy loss from the solar panel to the battery backup.
- Develop a mechanism which rotates the array of solar panels establishing the synchronous with the sunlight to obtain the maximum solar energy during 7.00 am to 4.00 pm instead of 10.00 am to 2.00 pm.

3. Methodology

The power loss is reduced by converting the input voltage from the solar panel array to AC . This converted input AC voltage is increased resulting in decrease in the current to minimise the power loss. The proposed model is as shown in the figure 1.

Figure 1: The proposed model which increases the efficiency

The solar panel is giving the output energy in either 12V as well as 24V in DC. This energy flows towards the storage unit through the copper connecting wires. The energy will be low voltage DC (either 12V or 24V) with high current (several Amp) if individually taken. If the panels are connected in series then the output voltage will be the sum of the individual panel voltage. In any case the current flow will be in amps which is considerably large The outdoor

unit containing the array of solar panels is installed in the rooftop and the storage unit and the inverter unit is installed in the power room. The distance between solar panel and battery backup is several meters. This setup requires the thick copper cable of a long distance to cover the rooftop and the battery bank. This cable is offering a considerable resistance when a current of several amp is flowing through it.

The power wasted in the form of heat through the conducting copper wire is

$$P=I^2R$$

Where I is the current flowing through the copper cable and R is the resistance of the copper cable. Since the current is in Amps there will be a considerable power loss because of the copper cable.

The model introduces an unit near the solar panel series which will increase the voltage and decrease the current before passing it on to the conducting media. The unit converts the DC voltage with high current into a high voltage AC signal with the low current. Since the power loss is directly proportional to the current flowing through the copper cable, the power loss is considerably reduced. This improves the efficiency of the solar panel and conducting media.

To synchronise the solar panel to the sunlight a rotating mechanism must be designed which will lock the panel to the sunlight. This results in panel facing towards sun during day time. This mechanism increases the production rate as the panel is exposed to sun light entirely during day time.

4. Analysis

The model is mainly used to decrease the current from Amp to milliamp by increasing the voltage. The conducting media is able to handle high voltage with low current. This high voltage with low current reduces the power loss at the conducting media. If the regular setup without the model is wasting say one amp of current in the form of heat, by using the model the current is reduced to mA resulting in 10% of the power wastage in the form of heat. This results in more power transferred to the battery backup than the wastage in the form of heat.

The rotary mechanism which locks the array of panels to sun light requires more power than the increase in the solar power production. This mechanism is not suitable even though the rate of the power generation is more than with out this mechanism.

4.1 Advantages

This model is useful to avoid the wastage of the power in the form of heat in the media. This model reduces the current and increases the voltage to avoid the power loss.

4.2 Benefits

This model is more useful in the places where the indoor unit is far away from the outdoor unit. If the distance is more then the connecting wire must be of a large size needs a small amount of current to pass through it resulting in less power loss. A large power generated from by the solar panel array needs this converter to increase the voltage and reduce the current to reduce the power loss.

4.3 Constraints

This model can not be generalised as the solar panel array will not be of same standard. Depending on the solar panel setup the model has to be designed.

4.4 Drawback

The purpose of the model is to reduce the power loss in the connecting media. The idea is to increase the voltage and decrease the current by converting the input DC to AC using transformer coupled oscillator. The most suitable converter circuit is the transformer coupled LC oscillator. This transformer couple itself wastes the power into heat. The purpose is to

reduce the power loss in the connecting media. To achieve this the model wastes the power from the transformer.

5. Conclusion

To avoid the power waste in the connecting media it is better to use the model which converts the input DC to AC and amplifies the voltage and reduces the current. The reduced current flowing in the conducting media reduces the power waste. However the circuit inside the model uses LC transformer coupled oscillator wastes some amount of energy in the form of heat.

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